

MORPHOMETRIC INDICATORS OF THE WASP SPECIES *VESPA ORIENTALIS* (LINNAEUS, 1771) IN THE SOUTHERN FERGANA REGION

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to the morphometric indicators of the wasp species *Vespa orientalis* in the Southern Fergana region. Measurements and analyses were conducted on the body length, weight, wing dimensions, leg length, and head width of queen, worker, and male specimens of *Vespa orientalis*.

Keywords: *Vespa orientalis*, social wasp, colony, morphometric analysis, Afrotropical region, queen, worker, mandible.

Introduction

Vespa orientalis (Linnaeus, 1771) is one of the social wasps belonging to the Vespidae family, known for its social behavior and significant role in ecosystems. This species is widespread in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, and exhibits a well-organized social system consisting of queens, workers, and males. Each caste (queen, worker, male) in the colony performs specific functions and has distinct morphological differences. The systematic classification of *Vespa orientalis* is as follows:

Class: Insecta

Order: Hymenoptera

Family: Vespidae

Subfamily: Vespinae

Genus: *Vespa*

Species: *Vespa orientalis* (Linnaeus, 1771)

Its general distribution includes the Afrotropical region (Bahrain, Ethiopia, Oman, Saudi Arabia, Somalia, UAE, Yemen; Madagascar – exotic), the Oriental region (India, Nepal), the Eastern region (Afghanistan, China, Iran, Pakistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan), and the Western Palearctic (Algeria, Cyprus, Egypt, Europe, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Libya, Russia, Syria, Turkey) regions [6].

The body length of *Vespa orientalis* ranges from 25 to 35 mm, with females typically larger than males. The body is divided into the head, thorax, and abdomen, characterized by a reddish-brown exoskeleton with bright yellow markings. The head is broad and large, with dark compound eyes that enhance vision. Its mandibles are well-developed, playing an essential role in nest building and hunting [1; 2].

There are three pairs of legs and two pairs of wings on the thorax. These two pairs of wings provide effective flight capabilities essential for foraging and defending the nest. The wings are semi-transparent with a brownish tint. The abdomen consists of multiple segments, each marked by distinctive yellow stripes that help in species identification.

One of the distinguishing features of *Vespa orientalis* is its specialized cuticle, which absorbs solar energy, aiding in thermoregulation and energy management during high-temperature activities [3; 4].

The final abdominal segment is equipped with a stinger, which is used for defense and capturing prey. Unlike bees, this stinger does not detach from the body, allowing the wasp to sting multiple times. This species prefers to build nests underground, forming colonies in dark, protected locations [5].

Samples were collected from natural ecosystems and agrocenoses in the Bagdad and Rishtan districts, Fergana city of Southern Fergana. Morphometric indicators were measured using a caliper. Each parameter was measured three times, and the average values were recorded. The measurements included body length (BL), body weight (BW), fore wing length (FWL), fore wing width (FWW), hind wing length (HWL), hind wing width (HWW), femur length (FL), tibia length (TL), and head width (HW).

The morphometric indicators of each sample were measured, and their average values were calculated (Table 1).

Table 1

Morphometric measurements of vespa orientalis specimens

№	Morphometric parameter	Queen (average)	Worker (average)	Male (average)
1	BL: Body length (mm)	28,8	19,2	20,5
2	BW: Body weight (mg)	470	230	250
3	FWL: Fore wing length (mm)	20,2	17,2	17,5
4	FWW: Fore wing width (mm)	5,9	4,9	5,1
5	HWL: Hind wing length (mm)	14,5	11,8	12,2
6	HWW: Hind wing width (mm)	4,2	3,7	3,8
7	FL: Femur length (mm)	8,6	7,4	7,7
8	TL: Tibia length (mm)	10,8	9,2	9,5
9	HW: Head width (mm)	6,1	4,7	5,0

The obtained morphometric data showed significant differences among the castes of *Vespa orientalis* (queen, male, worker), reflecting their adaptation to specialized roles within the colony. The larger body size and weight of the queens are crucial for their reproductive functions. These findings align with those of previous researchers, who have also highlighted the morphological characteristics adapted for the reproductive roles of queens (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Queen of *Vespa orientalis* A – external appearance, B – head and antennae. (Fergana region, Bagdad district, 22.09.2024., original photographs. [Photographer: Adkhamjon Rasuljonov].

The FWL (fore wing length) and FWW (fore wing width) indicators demonstrate differences in flight capabilities among the castes. Queens have larger wings necessary to lift their bodies, which is crucial during mating flights and the initial nest-building phase. Worker wasps have relatively smaller wings, which are adapted for quick and agile movements. This feature facilitates foraging and nest defense. Male wasps, while having similar wing dimensions to workers, have slightly longer FWL, which can support prolonged flights during mating.

The leg length measurements (FL and TL) also indicate functional adaptations. Queens possess slightly longer hind legs (TL), which may enhance mobility during egg-laying and movement within the nest. Shorter leg lengths in worker wasps are optimized for efficient movement during foraging and nest maintenance. The longer FL and TL in males could be advantageous during mating behaviors.

Conclusion: The results of the study showed that each caste is adapted to its specific roles within the colony. The queen, with a larger body and weight, is well-suited for reproduction and egg-laying. The smaller wings of workers facilitate rapid movement and foraging activities. Males have slightly longer wings and legs, which are beneficial for mating flights and behaviors.

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